

ISic0513

Honours for Gaius Bultius Geminius Titianus

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.11.12 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo Civico di Marsala

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

A in lines 2, 5 and 7 has broken bar

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. C(aio) · Bultio · Geminiꝰ
2. Titiano · proco(n)s(uli)
3. prov(inciae) Sicil(iae) · co(n)s(uli) · c(larissimo) v(iro) ·
4. ob · insignem · eius
5. benivolentiambenevolentiam
6. erga ordinem et
7. patriam · XII · trib(us) ·
8. patrono · merenti ·

Apparatus

text from photograph

Translation (en)

To Caius Bultius Geminus Titianus, proconsul of the province of Sicily, consularis and vir clarissimus, on account of his distinguished goodwill towards the ordo and his fatherland. The twelve tribes (set this up) to their deserving patron.

Commentary

The son of this individual is honoured in a second inscription from Mazara, ISic0486 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0486>]

Digital identifiers:

TM 491738

EDCS 22000819

Bibliography

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C. BAETHO GEMINUS
P. P. ANNO PRO COS
PROV. SIGINTORUM
OB IN SIGNINENSIS
BENIVOLENTIAM
ERGA ORDINEM ET
PATRIAM XII TABIS
PATRONO MERENTI

Photo R.J.A. Wilson